

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TOURISM COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. International tourism, as one of the biggest and the most dynamic industries in the world, inevitably influences all the aspects of social life, including language. The development of international tourism has given rise to increase in professional communication in the field. A large number of tourism terms is continually coined, increasing scientific interest in the questions of translating and borrowing tourist terminology into different languages.

Keywords: language, society, tourism, term, word stock, linguocultural, development, linguistic, extralinguistic, ethnography, toponymy.

INTRODUCTION

Language and society are inextricably linked and all the changes that take place in the society are reflected in the language the society use. The language uses its “inner” linguistic resources when new concepts appear. In addition to them, other language resources as word stock can be addressed to, for instance, to borrow words from. It is a widely-used process for many languages and the Uzbek language is not an exception from this.

This, in turn, ensures that the word stock of the language is enriched with new lexical (phraseological) units that can be developed in a linguocultural environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Obviously, it is important to consider the reasons of borrowings as a purely linguistic process. They are closely interrelated being divided into ...non-linguistic (extralinguistic) and linguistic factors.

There are specific words that are actively used within each sphere and specific to that sphere.

The term as a lexical unit belonging to a limited lexical layer, is the main object of terminological research and an important source of terminological dictionaries.

In books on Linguistics, the following issues as close political, economic and cultural ties between

nations, internal social relations are mentioned as non-linguistic factors of lexical borrowings. Moreover, economic and political changes in the society that borrow a word, the role of language in the economic environment of the society are the components of the extralinguistic branch of the language. The language recipient simultaneously adopts both new things and concepts and their linguistic expression (words) [1]. In this sense, lexical units and terms as well can be borrowed.

According to R. Jomonov, ‘The most important non-linguistic (extralinguistic) factors in borrowings are political, economic and cultural ties between people; scientific development; the expansion of the activity of the mass media; increasing demand for translated literature; texts in advertisement and visual aids; the growing demand for foreign languages and so on.’[3] One of the intensively enriching spheres of terminology with lexical units is tourism terminology [2].

RESULTS AND DISSUSSION

Tourism terms can be genetically divided into the following groups in Uzbek:

- 1) tourism terms in Uzbek that has existed for a long time;
- 2) simple tourism terms, which are directly borrowed from foreign languages.

1. *Bayram – “a holiday”, bojxona - “customs house”, buyurtma*

– “an order”, *mablag’ - “funds” etc* were formed on the basis of the internal potentials of the Uzbek language. Many observations of the formation of terms by the suffix method in Russian and English were noted in the works analyzed above.

2. The problem of adopting tourism terminology of the Uzbek language it was found that borrowing of direct terms is active.

When a term is directly adopted, it is borrowed without any change or with some (partial) phonetic change.

The following lexical units in tourism terminology belong to the following types: *apartment, guide, tabloid, timeshare, transit, transfer, charter, deluxe, aerobics, aerodrome, aerophobia, airplane, airport, airline ticket, airline, air fare, auto camping, auto rally, bus station* and so on.

As it is observed in Russian and English, there are dominant terms in Uzbek tourism terminology and a great number of compounds are formed with their

participation. These include terms such as “**tourist**”, “**tourism**”, “**tour**”, “**number**” and “**class**”. The terms formed in Uzbek with the component *tourism* are numerous: *turistik bozor* (*tourism market*), *turistik faoliyat* (*tourism activity*), *turistik faoliyat sub’ektlari* (*subjects of tourist activity*), *turistik guruh rahbari* (*guide*), *turistik kema* (*tourist vessel*), *turistik industriya* (*tourist industry*), *turistik klass* (*tourist class*), *turistik klass mehmonxonasi* (*tourist class hotel*), *turistik kompleks* (*tourist complex*), *turistik mahsulot* (*tourist product*), *turistik mahsulot faoliyati* (*tourist product activity*), *turistik mahsulotni tashkillashtirish* (*tourist product development*), *turistik markaz* (*tourist centre*), *turistik marshrut* (*tourist route*), *turistik oqim* (*tourist flow*), *turistik paket* (*tourist package*), *turistik qiziqish* (*tourist interest*), *turistik yig‘im* (*tourist collection*) and so on.

The existence of several types of tourism necessitates the existence of the terms compounded with *tourism*: *child safe tourism*, *extreme tourism*, *gastronomic tourism*, *military tourism*, *amateur tourism*, *domestic tourism*, *social tourism*, *individual tourism*, *caravan tourism*, *congress tourism*, *cultural tourism*, *national tourism*, *museum tourism*, *wedding tourism*, *advertising tourism*, *industrial tourism*, *adventure tourism*, *health tourism*, *mountain tourism*, *small tourism zones* etc.

Special lexical units formed with the participation of the terms *tour*, *number*, *class* are mainly the terms that are actively used in tourism services: *tour police*, *tour package*, *tour organizer*, *tour guide*; *single room*, *double room*, *deluxe room*, *balcony*, *presidential room*, *triple room*, *quadruple room*, *tourist class*, *first class*, *middle first class*, *middle tourist class*, *second class*, *high quality tourist class* and so on.

While a commonly used word is accepted as a term, only one of the meanings of that word will depend on the concept that the term means. The reason is that the term should be concise, clear, unambiguous and uniform.

Examples for commonly used tourist terms are: *hotel*, *room*, *transport*,

season, dormitory, city tour, tourist, religious pilgrimage, mausoleum, monument, corner room, double room, triple room, quadruple room , dormitory, extra bed, family room, floor key and passenger. These units occur as terms related to tourism.

CONSLUSION

To conclude, Uzbek tourism terminology differs from other terminological systems in that it is open and has a fast enriching tendency. The fact that comparative research on tourism terminology in world linguistics, carried out shows that the terminology of this sphere is arranged in a certain sense, certain principles have been developed in naming of emerging concepts. In particular, non-linguistic factors, along with linguistic factors, play an important role in the development and progress of Uzbek tourism terminology.

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